

ISic0627

I.Sicily inscription 0627

Language

Latin

Type

honorific

Material

marble (white)

Object

statue base

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lilybaeum

Place of origin (modern)

Marsala

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Trapani, Museo Regionale
Agostino Pepoli, inventory 5304

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: EDR072108

1. T (ito) Fulvio Aurelio
2. Antonino
3. Imp (eratoris) Caes (aris) M (arci) Aureli Antonini
4. Aug (usti) filio
5. L (ucius) Aponius Rufinus,
6. ob honorem seviratus,
7. pec (unia) sua.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 284555

EDR 072108
EDCS 16600237

Bibliography

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